

Monolithic fingers with actively variable compliance for underactuated tendon-driven robotic grippers

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Abstract—Underactuated tendon-driven fingers are a simple, yet effective solution, for realizing robotic grippers and hands. The lack of controllable degrees of actuation and precise sensing is compensated by the deformable structure of the finger, which is able to adapt to the objects to be grasped and manipulated, and also to implement grasping strategies based on environmental constraint exploitation. One of the main drawbacks of these robotic fingers is that, due to the limited number of actuators, they can only realize a limited number of movements. Finger closure motion realized by activating the tendon depends on finger mechanical properties, and in particular on elastic joint stiffness. In this paper, we introduce grippers with monolithic fingers in which the stiffness of the flexible parts can be actively regulated by applying a pre-compression to the structure, controlled by a twisted-string actuator (TSA). The paper introduces the main idea of this type of gripper, the working principle of the joint, and presents some preliminary investigations on the relationship between pre-compression and flexural stiffness.

Index Terms—Robotic grippers, grasping and manipulation, soft robots, twisted string actuators

I. WORK DESCRIPTION

In this paper, we present a possible solution for controlling closure motion in underactuated tendon-driven robotic fingers, based on the application of a controllable pre-compression to their flexible parts.

The gripper that has been considered in this study is composed of monolithic fingers composed of a sequence of thicker, rigid parts and thinner, wave-shaped flexible parts. This structure has been introduced and investigated in [1]. Each finger is tendon actuated: a tendon is connected on one side at the fingertip, it passes through the finger structure and is connected, on the other side, to a pulley connected to a motor. Activating the motor, the tendon is pulled producing finger flexion. Finger extension is passively obtained by releasing the tendon. More specifically, the flexible parts of the fingers have a sinusoidal wave shape created and parametrically defined as a function of a few parameters.

In [1] we characterized the bending stiffness of the flexible part of the monolithic fingers, analyzing how this parameter is affected by its geometrical parameters. In [2] we showed also how by regulating the stiffness in the proximal joint of a finger composed of three modules we can obtain different

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Fig. 1: Structure of a gripper with two monolithic fingers in which the stiffness of the proximal flexible part can be regulated by applying a pre-compression.

Fig. 2: Results of flexible wave-shaped experimental characterization: deflection angle as a function of tendon activation for different values of wave pre-compression.

fingertip trajectories. Fig. 2 reports an example relative to a finger with two flexible wave-shaped parts in which the proximal one has an actively variable stiffness: by increasing the stiffness of the proximal part fingertip trajectory changes, in particular, trajectory curvature increases, providing to the gripper a power-grasp closure shape.

In general, bending stiffness depends also on the loads applied to the flexible elements. Specifically, by applying a pre-compression to the flexible part, it's possible to modify its bending stiffness, as verified in [3], [2]. In such works, we exploited the possibility of actively modifying the pre-compression, even during task execution, by means of twisted string actuators (TSA).

The TSA converts the rotary motion into linear by twisting a set of parallel strings (two in our case) that are connected on one side to a motor on the other to a linear moving element. The linear motion is generated by the geometrical

Fig. 3: First row: results of FEM analysis. Second row: results of experimental characterization (a,d) $n_r = 3$, (b,e) $n_r = 4$, (c,f) $n_r = 5$ (b,e) $n_r = 4$. Pre-compression is obtained by activating the TSA motor with the following current values: $\tau_1 = 12mA$, $\tau_2 = 38mA$, $\tau_3 = 80mA$, $\tau_4 = 160mA$, $\tau_5 = 290mA$.

string configuration that during the twist passes from a straight line to a helix in which the pitch is decreased as the twist increases, generating a contraction. The main advantage of TSA is that small-size motors with high speed and low torque can be used to create a very high force and, moreover a cheap, lightweight, and compact linear transmission system [4], [5], [6].

In Fig. 1 we report the structure of a gripper with two fingers, where a pre-compression of the proximal flexible parts is realized by two (TSA).

The stiffness of the flexible part in the longitudinal direction (normal stiffness) can be approximately evaluated as:

$$k_w = \frac{2E_w J}{n_s h^3}, \quad (1)$$

where E_w is the Young's coefficient for joint material and J is wave cross-section moment of inertia, ($J = \frac{wt^3}{12}$.)

This simplified expression for the normal stiffness is based on the hypothesis that when a compression or tension load is applied to the wave-joint, the wave ridges are subject to a pure bending solicitation. The stiffness k_w can be considered approximately constant until the ridges assume a "packed" configuration. By compressing the wave joint, its length decreases and it becomes stiffer in the bending direction. The relationship between normal load and bending stiffness is not linear.

In [3] we performed an identification of its force/deflection behavior in different operative conditions, both numerically and by means of direct measures on finger prototypes. The results of the experimental characterization performed on three elements with different geometrical characteristics are reported in Fig. 3, where the deflection angle as a function of tendon activation is reported for different values of pre-compression

Fig. 4: CAD models of the three analyzed elements, with $n_s = 3$, $n_s = 4$, and $n_s = 5$.

applied to the wave-shaped flexible part. The 3D-CAD models of the three elements are reported in Fig. 4.

The pre-compression is realized with a TSA-based actuator, that is particularly compact. Stiffness regulation does not require high dynamics properties, so the TSA motor can be sufficiently small to be easily embedded inside the rigid parts of the modules composing the finger.

The finger maintains a modular structure, in which, depending on the specific application, it is possible to a priori define which joints should have a variable stiffness and the ones in which it can be maintained constant, so as to keep as limited as possible the number of actuators. Previous works, for instance in [7], showed in particular that in a soft-rigid structure, the joint whose stiffness mostly influences the closure motion is the proximal one. Activating the stiffness of the proximal joint does not significantly increase finger mechanical complexity, since the TSA motor is on the base structure of the finger.

The possibility of regulating passive joint compliance could be provided to a limited number of joints only, preferably

the proximal ones. The increase in complexity, in this case, is not so critical. Furthermore, in some cases in which the presence of actuators and electronics components close to the fingers could be a problem (e.g. in food handling, underwater manipulation, etc.), and if such a regulation is required *una tantum*, stiffness regulation could be realized manually, for instance by means of a screw.

It's worth observing that adding a pre-compression to the joint increases the overall stress status of the joint and could lead to mechanical failures or mechanical fatigue. This issue should be further investigated in future developments of this work and could be mitigated by using fatigue-resistant materials.

Besides the stiffness, adding a pre-compression to the wave-joint also produces a change in joint length and an overall variation of finger dimensions. This effect could be properly managed by a robot arm control system or by the grasp planner. Moreover, rather than a drawback, this effect could be an opportunity and further exploited in in-hand manipulation tasks, for instance developing algorithms inspired by the caterpillar locomotion strategy [8]. In future developments of this work, we will further investigate how tendon actuation and stiffness regulation can be dynamically combined in grasping and in-hand manipulation tasks.

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